

Tata Institute of social sciences

Evaluation Report: TISS

Submitted to:

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Written by

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1. History & Introduction

The Tata Institute of Social Sciences (TISS) was established in 1936 as the Sir Dorabji Tata Graduate School of Social Work. In 1944, it was renamed as the Tata Institute of Social Sciences. The Institute shifts to a new campus at Deonar, Mumbai in 1954 at present this is the Main Campus of the Institute. The year 1964 was an important landmark in the history of the Institute, when it was declared Deemed to be a University under Section 3 of the University Grants Commission Act (UGC), 1956.

Since its beginning, the TISS has been working to be an institution of excellence in higher education that continually responds to changing social realities through the development and application of knowledge, towards creating a people-centered, ecologically sustainable and just society that promotes and protects dignity, equality, social justice and human rights for all. Afterwards In 2002 The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) award a 5-Star rating to the Institute.

<https://www.tiss.edu/search/>

Prof Shalini Bharat (Vice-Chancellor, Director)
Campuses Mumbai, Tuljapur, Hyderabad, Guwahati

2. Governance & ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURE

The institute has a governing board nominated by the Government of India, Government of Maharashtra, the University of Mumbai and the University grants commission along with representatives from similar to that of the chancellor of a conventional university. The academic council decides the institute faculty. S. Ramadorai, vice chairperson, TCS and Advisor to the Prime Minister of India, is the current honorary chairperson of TISS. The chairperson of the governing board has responsibility of academic work and comprises faculty drawn from the institute's 4 campuses and as well as 6 external experts.

The Director, as the Vice-Chancellor of the Institute, works with the Deputy Directors of all 4 campuses and the Registrar to lead the Institute.

Academic Structure The academic structure of the Institute consists of Deputy Directors of campuses, Deans of Schools, and Chairpersons of Independent Centres.

Governing Board: The Governing Board, as the highest executive body, plays the pivotal role of laying down policies, both academic and governance.

Academic Council: The Academic Council deliberates on matters of academic nature and steers the Institute to maintain academic standards of excellence. The Council approves the academic programmes of all Schools/Centres and provides directions for future academic growth and development.

Vision & Mission

In pursuance of its vision and guiding principles, the Tata Institute of Social Sciences organizes teaching programmes to facilitate the development of competent and committed professionals for practice, research and teaching; undertakes research; develops and disseminates knowledge; and reaches out to the larger community through extension, at the local, national, regional and international levels.

Vision of the TISS has been to be an institution of excellence in higher education that continually responds to changing social realities through the development and application of knowledge, towards creating a people-centered, ecologically sustainable and just society that promotes and protects dignity, equality, social justice and human rights for all. The TISS works towards its vision through:

- Creation and provision of socially relevant and high quality professional education in a wide range of inter-disciplinary areas of Social Sciences to a larger number of students from all sections of the society in the country.
- Facilitation of autonomous research and dissemination of knowledge.
- Support knowledge creation through strong M.Phil. And Ph.D. programmes and Post-Doctoral scholars.
- Strategic extension, field action and advocacy through training and capacity building of State and non-State institutions and personnel.
- Initiate field action and advocacy to demonstrate and facilitate creation of policies and programmes.
- Professional response to natural and human-made disasters, through participation in relief and rehabilitation activities

3. Functions

Academic

The Tata institute has 21 schools, 45 centres and 8 independent centres. The Institute is designated as a Curriculum Development Centre for Social Work Education by the UGC. Master's degree programmes in Health Administration and in Hospital

Administration are initiated. The institute allots programmes in Masters Courses, Doctoral Courses, Short-term Courses and online Courses. TISS also provides a fellowship programme in Dialogues in Criminal Justice and Rehabilitation.

Research

The Office of Research and Development has started a Working Paper (WP) Series to provide a platform to M.Phil/PhD students and young researchers to disseminate and document their ongoing research work, which has not been published so far. The papers are published electronically and are available online.

Over the years, through its research in social work, social sciences, human resources management, health systems and allied fields, the TISS has made consistent contributions to public sector, civil society and the development sector and helped shape planning, policy and programme formulation, foster critical rethinking and development of people-centered interventions.

Collaboration

Collaboration with International Federation of Red Cross and Crescent Societies (IFRC), Collaboration with Universities in USA *Like*, University of Chicago, Chicago, USA, **Collaboration with Universities in Europe** *Like*, London School of Economics, London, **Collaboration with Universities in Australia** *Like*, Victoria University, Australia, **Collaboration with Universities in other countries** Critical Edge Alliance - An alliance of progressive Universities in USA, Denmark, Brazil, Columbia, Morocco and India.

Projects

ICALL: psychosocial helpline for troubled souls, **Amulya Balpan, Koshish:** initiative on homeless and destitution, **Pragati:** Integrated rural health and development project, **Prayas:** Social work demonstration project.

Initiatives

Incubation Centre: To support social entrepreneurship where the students, immediately after graduation, get guidance, mentoring, physical space and networking, **Connected Learning Initiative (CLIX):** To offer scalable and sustainable quality teaching and learning experiences for English, mathematics and science with values and hand on work, **Mahatma Gandhi Academy for Human Development (MGAHD), Early Literacy Initiative, Saksham, Tata Institute of Social Sciences:** Saksham has three major grants in the area of HIV & TB counseling, capacity building and community engagement.

Conferences and seminars

Conferences and seminars are held by TISS at national as well as international level.

Publication

It has published over a 100 books and monographs. The Publications Unit has been publishing The **Indian Journal of Social Work (IJSW)** uninterruptedly since 1940. Quarterly publishes by TISS.

TISS also publishes annual report, program reports, national report, E-magazines, articles, press releases and Prayas newsletter.

Library

The Sir Dorabji Tata Memorial Library (SDTML) continues to be proactive in supporting new academic developments at the institute. Its resources and services are aimed at providing the highest level of research and teaching support to all the programmes of the Institute. The s collection is reviewed every year in order for it to be relevant to the emerging and developing areas of research. It holds about 1, 20,000 volumes, and subscribes to over 8,500 print and e-journals.

Computer Centre

The Institute has an in-house data center which hosts all its servers. All critical software applications are developed, hosted and maintained in-house. The computer centre extensively promotes the use of free and open source software.

4. Conclusion

TISS is a unique institution that brings together high quality scholars and practitioners from Social, Economic, Political, Physical, Habitat, Engineering, Health, and Environmental Sciences to co-create teaching and research programmes to address the most critical current and emerging issues of the nation. It is one of the key universities supported by the UGC/Ministry of Education in the disciplinary and inter-disciplinary areas of Social Sciences that provides teaching and research to build human service professionals for the social sector. **Forbes India** named TISS a 'Great Place to Study' in a 2018 feature on Indian Institutes. The Institute is ranked at 34 among all Indian universities by NIRF in 2020. Also, TISS has been awarded the highest ranking 'Diamond Ranking (Overall)' in the QS-I Gauge rating process.

5. Reference

<https://tiss.edu/search/>